

Recognizing and Rewarding Peer Review of Scholarly Articles, Books, and Funding Proposals

RECOMMENDATIONS BY THE COARA WORKING GROUP ON
RECOGNIZING AND REWARDING PEER REVIEW

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Chapter 1: Overview

Aims and Scope

Peer review – the critical assessment of research outputs and funding proposals by subject matter experts within the relevant fields – stands as a fundamental pillar of academic and scientific evaluation. This process plays a dual role: it contributes to both the quality and integrity of research outputs, as well as the cumulative evaluation of researchers in grant peer review through formal committees and hiring processes. Peer review is essential to the academic ecosystem, providing a mechanism for maintaining rigorous standards and fostering scholarly dialogue. It is the bedrock of decisions on what gets published, funded, or recognized within academia. The peer review system is in urgent need of reform due to a combination of structural inefficiencies and evolving challenges in the research landscape. Currently, disproportionate value is placed on the number of publications in select high-impact journals, a practice that not only skews academic incentives but also consolidates the power of publishing companies over the peer review process. As the volume of scientific output rapidly expands, the system is becoming overburdened. We believe that improvements in the peer review system, which are being developed, would benefit from further consolidation and uptake by the various stakeholders.

However, despite its central role in academic and scientific progress, peer review is often underappreciated and insufficiently recognized within formal academic structures. Scholars undertake peer review as a professional obligation and a means to advance their fields, yet these contributions are rarely acknowledged or rewarded in meaningful ways. This lack of recognition not only undervalues the contributions of reviewers, but also stifles the potential for improving peer review processes, which are essential for ensuring fair and transparent research assessment. Proper recognition and reward of peer review will improve its quality and thus contribute to a better open research ecosystem. Mechanisms for monitoring and evaluation of these changes should be put in place.

The Coalition on Advancing Research Assessment ([CoARA](#)) formed a working group on “[Recognizing and Rewarding Peer Review](#)” to tackle these challenges. The group’s primary objective is to develop actionable guidelines that key stakeholders – including research funding organizations, editors/publishers, research performing organizations, and reviewers—can adopt. Peer review is an integral part of the research process—and deserves to be recognized as such. By integrating recognition and reward systems for peer review into the academic credit framework, the goal is to indirectly improve the quality and reliability of both the review process and the research it assesses: fostering a better recognition environment for peer review will also contribute to researchers spending more attention and time on this crucial task.

However, it is important to state from the outset that it is beyond the scope of this paper to exactly define what peer review is, or what characterizes the quality of a ‘high-quality’ peer review: the answers to that question vary widely as a function of disciplines and epistemic traditions and are the responsibility of individual editors. We take peer review, with all its flaws and limitations, to be an integral part of the collaborative research process that leads to a published paper. The contributions of the reviewers in this process are as important as those of the author. These contributions are typically evaluated by the handling editor who is mediating the dialogue between the author and the reviewers. As a result, we believe that the editorial evaluation of reviews could be made more visible in order to properly recognize all contributions to the paper. We thus wish to create more visibility and recognition for the reviewing process and its outputs, without setting standards for the content of these outputs. Similarly, we will not engage in a discussion of the merits of closed, open, or transparent peer review,¹ noting simply that for peer review to be properly acknowledged and recognized, it must be made available in some form.

This paper specifically focuses on recognizing and rewarding peer review for scholarly outputs such as manuscripts (including scholarly articles and preprints), books, and funding proposals. The recommendations are limited to these formats as they represent the most common intellectual products across various academic disciplines. The recommendations do not cover informal post-publication commenting, social media, or other types of peer feedback, they do not include ethics reviews or the reviews of performative practices nor technical curation or editorial work. Our recommendations are designed to resonate with other sectors that utilize peer review. The paper is structured to address peer review in scholarly manuscripts, followed by books, and then funding proposals. A major challenge in the peer review system is the rise in submission volumes. Furthermore, an increasingly competitive publishing process – due to increased volumes, but also the continued dependency of research assessment of “metricized” publishing output – have led to an unsustainable burden on the peer review system.

Table 1 (see pp. 7-11) summarizes general recommendations categorized by the three main stakeholder groups involved in scholarly peer review. We also provide specific recommendations tailored to scholarly manuscripts, books, and funding proposals, each organized by stakeholder groups. These recommendations are intended to be systematic, practical, scalable, and broadly applicable across different disciplines.

In conclusion, our recommendations aim to advance the recognition and rewarding of peer review, sparking meaningful change within academic culture. The working group is committed to driving these changes, recognizing that the future of academic

¹ For the benefits of open peer review, see Schmidt B, Ross-Hellauer T, van Edig X, Moylan EC. Ten considerations for open peer review. *F1000Res*. 2018 Jun 29;7:969. doi: 10.12688/f1000research.15334.1. PMID: 30135731; PMCID: PMC6073088, and Polka et al. (2018: <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-06032-w>)

scholarship depends on our ability to evolve and enhance the structures that support it.

Terms and Definitions

- **Reward:** Refers to tangible or career-related benefits given to reviewers in exchange for their time, expertise, and effort. These may include: professional incentives, such as consideration for promotions, tenure, research assessments, or financial compensation.
- **Recognition:** Refers to the formal or informal acknowledgment of a reviewer's contributions, which can positively impact their academic standing and professional reputation. This may include acknowledgment of reviewing, alongside teaching and research, as a scholarly output with appropriate time allocation, acknowledgments in publications, as well as tokens of appreciation such as badges or certificates.
- **Peer review:** The process by which an expert (peer) evaluates a scholarly manuscript (article, preprint, or conference proceeding), book, or funding proposal. Peer review of an article, book or funding proposal assesses the quality, and importance of its claims, hypotheses, research questions, and the empirical support for the claims made, as a function of the reviewers knowledge of the field, its accepted standards, and its epistemic traditions. The goal of peer review is to help authors improve, refine, and correct their contributions. In most cases, the expert (peer) is invited by an editor who considers their expertise, impartiality, potential conflicts of interest, and reliability.
- **Open peer review:** A peer review process where review reports, along with the identities of the reviewers, are published openly alongside the paper or preprint, with or without the author's responses. These reports are typically made public only if the article is accepted and published. Open peer review systems involving preprints may allow for the posting of referee comments on the preprint version, thus addressing the limitation of foregone credit for reviewers of rejected papers.
- **Transparent peer review:** A variation of 'open peer review' where the review reports are published openly alongside the paper or preprint, without revealing the identities of the reviewers. This approach maintains reviewer anonymity while providing transparency in the review process.
- **Closed peer review:** A peer review process where the review reports are not published openly, and the identities of reviewers remain hidden for the authors, while the identity of the author may or may not be available to the reviewers (e.g. single blind/ masked or double blind/ masked peer review).
- **Scholarly articles:** Publication types that undergo academic peer review, including research papers, review articles, and other shorter publication formats. These articles present original research, analysis, or synthesis of existing

knowledge in a structured and rigorous manner.

- **Refereed preprint:** A preprint version of a scholarly manuscript that has undergone formal peer review, with referee comments posted alongside the preprint, with or without author responses. This format combines the rapid dissemination of preprints with the quality assurance of peer review.
- **Publishing:** The stable, citable public dissemination of a scholarly article or book, whether peer-reviewed or not. Publication often involves selection based on quality and other attributes, in accordance with the policies of a publisher, journal, or other platform. This process aims to ensure the wide distribution and accessibility of scholarly work.
- **Funding proposals:** Formal written requests for financial support submitted to research funding organizations by individuals or research groups at research performing organizations (private or public). These proposals typically outline a research project or research infrastructure that requires funding, detailing objectives, methodologies, expected outcomes, and budget requirements.

Stakeholder Groups

The recommendations provided in this document are targeted at the following stakeholder groups:

- **Research performing organizations (RPOs):** Institutions responsible for assessing individual researchers during hiring, promotion decisions, and annual appraisals. They establish criteria, select relevant institutional indicators, and determine resource allocation – all of which have significant downstream effects on the evaluation and development of researchers within the organization.
- **Research funding organizations (RFOs – public and private):** Entities responsible for evaluating funding proposals and individual applicants. They coordinate peer review processes for funding applications, establish assessment criteria, and make funding allocation decisions that significantly impact research directions and careers.
- **Editors, publishers, journals, and other platforms:** Organizations and individuals responsible for coordinating the peer review process of scholarly articles, books, and other academic outputs. They establish review guidelines, select reviewers, manage the review process, and make publication decisions that influence the dissemination and impact of research.
- **Researchers:** Individual researchers who conduct peer review activities as part of their professional responsibilities. They evaluate the quality, validity, and significance of research in their field, provide feedback to improve scholarly work, and contribute to the collective knowledge validation process. These activities are often listed as part of their professional accomplishments and factor into their own career progression.

- **Research support staff:** Grant officers, data stewards, lab assistants, privacy officers, and open science experts, among others, who review projects and funding proposals before submission, and often contribute to increasing the quality of proposals (see <https://doi.org/10.36850/mr8>).

Table 1: Template for Recognizing and Rewarding Peer Review Activities in Research Assessment

Table 1 offers a suggestive, rather than prescriptive, general template outlining potential responsibilities and actions for key stakeholders in developing a systemic approach to recognizing and rewarding peer review activities across scholarly manuscripts, books, and funding proposals within research assessment processes. The guidelines are not intended as fixed directives, instead they should be seen as an adaptable framework. Attributes and recommendations may require adaptation to align with the diverse practices, norms, and contexts of different disciplines, geographies, and resource-contexts. This template is meant to provide a foundational reference, encouraging stakeholders to thoughtfully customize their approaches to reflect the specific needs and values of their respective fields.

	Organizations that perform research assessment (RPOs and RFOs)	Organizations that coordinate and/or conduct peer review (publishers, RPOs, RFOs)	Researchers (as reviewers)
Openness	<p>Encourage researchers to perform peer review for publishers and platforms that support transparent or open peer review.</p> <p>Consider the balance between the burden of peer review and the purpose of evaluation. For example, small seed-funding grants for high-risk ideas may only require a basic fit-for-purpose check rather than full peer review, which may help to conserve resources.</p>	<p>Support transparent or open peer review.</p> <p>Allow reviewers to sign their reviews.</p>	<p>Perform peer review for platforms that support transparent or open peer review.</p> <p>A moderate approach to openness is signing closed reviews by name, even if not publicly disclosed.</p>
Credit and recognition	<p>Encourage peer review for organizations that credit reviewers by actively promoting engagement with editors, publishers, platforms,</p>	<p>Create a transparent credit policy that clearly defines and communicates how, and in what form, credit will be given to reviewers.</p>	<p>Prioritize engaging in peer review for publishers, platforms, and RFOs offering formal credit and recognition.</p>

	<p>and funders that recognize reviewer contributions.</p> <p>Develop CV templates and assessment forms that capture peer review activities, emphasizing quality and impact without over-relying on metrics.</p> <p>Ensure transparency in peer review assessment by clearly communicating how peer review is evaluated in research assessments, including scoring mechanisms, weighting, and feedback.</p> <p>Include peer review in job evaluations by acknowledging peer review as a valuable academic contribution in job advertisements and evaluations.</p> <p>Establish clear guidelines for peer review activity, balancing quantity with quality considerations to set expectations for peer review engagement. Develop balanced evaluation systems that consider both quantity and quality of peer reviews without over-relying on metrics.</p> <p>Support open peer review systems by encouraging participation in transparent processes that allow for quality assessment of reviews.</p> <p>Emphasize peer review as an academic responsibility by encouraging researchers to</p>	<p>Specify whether the credit is limited to the journal or funding body, or if it can be shared publicly and with other institutions, ensuring transparency in the recognition process.</p> <p>Develop and implement a system that offers verifiable credit to peer reviewers, which they can include in their own research assessments. This could include evaluating their performance, providing qualitative feedback, or issuing certificates that recognize their contributions.</p> <p>Ensure that the credit given to reviewers is made public when appropriate. Clearly define whether the recognition is intrinsic (limited to the journal or funding body) or extrinsic (can be shared publicly or with other institutions) and specify with whom this information will be shared.</p> <p>Offer reviewers qualitative feedback, signed by the responsible review requester. This feedback can be provided on a per-article basis or as a cumulative summary, and reviewers can use it in their portfolios or for further professional development.</p>	<p>Report and regularly update peer review activities in CVs, assessment forms, and personal webpages such as one's ORCID record.</p> <p>Actively request feedback, evaluative acknowledgements, or certificates from the organizations for which peer review is performed, and ensure that these acknowledgments are included in professional documentation. Where possible, request that reviews be assigned a DOI or linked to the DOI tree of the published paper, thus enabling proper acknowledgment in CVs and citeability.</p> <p>While advocating for recognition, maintain the integrity of blind peer review where it is applied. Understand that in these cases, recognition may be more challenging to document publicly, but organizations can still offer internal certificates or feedback while preserving anonymity.</p>
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	view peer review as an integral part of academic life, focusing on integrity and quality, rather than career advancement.		
Support, infrastructure, and training	<p>Support the development of infrastructures for transparent or open peer review and for crediting and recognizing reviewers.</p> <p>Provide comprehensive training to researchers to adopt and use these infrastructures, distinguishing between the training of early career researchers (ECRs) and the continuing education of senior researchers, both of which are essential.</p> <p>Emphasize the importance of training professional and administrative staff on the fundamentals of the peer review system. This process should be twofold: central administrative and/or governance bodies should allocate resources and prioritize this training, while scholars who should be recognized and rewarded for their efforts, should lead the training initiatives.</p>	<p>Develop infrastructures for transparent or open peer review and for crediting and recognizing reviewers.</p> <p>Train researchers to adopt and use these infrastructures.</p> <p>Develop mentorship programs, where seasoned reviewers support ECRs.</p> <p>Adopt policies that explicitly encourage reviews that are co-authored by a mentor and their mentee in a documentable manner that allows credit to be extended to the co-referee.</p>	<p>Participate in training in the use of infrastructures for open peer review and for crediting and recognizing reviewers.</p> <p>Encourage the training of ECRs in (open) peer review practices.</p> <p>Mentor and support ECRs in (open) peer review.</p>
Fairness and sustainability	<p>Be transparent about the contributions and commitment researchers are expected to make to foster a fair and sustainable peer review system, and which reviews will impact their research assessment. For example, consider providing protected time for researchers to conduct peer reviews and explicitly including peer review responsibilities in their official research duties,</p>	<p>Provide information about the potential impact a review report could have on reviewers' future assessments as part of hiring, promotion, and funding decisions.</p> <p>Track and monitor the geographic, gender, and career stage diversity of reviewer pools and make concerted efforts to invite a broader range of reviewers to reflect the</p>	<p>Develop an appropriate ratio between research and peer review activities to maintain a balance between submissions and reviews. For example, for every submission an author makes, they could consider engaging in one or more peer review activities to keep the system in balance. The burden of peer review is often disproportionately placed on a small group of</p>

	<p>rather than treating it as a voluntary activity performed in their free time.</p> <p>Provide guidelines and training on what constitutes a reasonable balance between research and peer review activities, particularly tailored to different career stages to help researchers manage their time effectively while contributing meaningfully to the peer review process.</p>	<p>authorship of the published output.</p> <p>Actively include individuals from various backgrounds, career stages, genders, geographic locations, and under-represented groups in the peer review process.</p>	<p>researchers, which can lead to burnout and a lack of diverse perspectives in the evaluation of research.</p>
Assessment	<p>Enable/encourage/mandate the registration of peer review activities in the organization’s current research information system.</p> <p>In the assessment process of researchers, consider their reported peer review activity and their published review reports, and recognize them for these contributions. For example, RPOs can influence the registration and reporting of peer review activity in their annual performance and development conversation. By measuring the volume of peer review activity as an initial step, and potentially incorporating quality indicators as a follow-up, these reporting practices can naturally support the recognition and rewarding of peer review contributions.</p> <p>Consider incorporating editorial assessments of referees by journals and funders into qualitative or quantitative assessment processes. Advocate for</p>	<p>Enable editors to collect and share external editorial assessments that evaluate and recognize the contribution of the reviews/reviewers. Aim for the standardization of such assessments to allow for systematic use in the research assessment of referees.</p> <p>Provide reviewers with constructive feedback to help them improve their reviewing skills. This feedback could be shared privately with the individual reviewers.</p> <p>Offer public recognition for exemplary reviewers, such as publishing a list of outstanding reviewers annually or awarding certificates of excellence, taking into account the diversity of people and roles as well as their capacity to participate.</p> <p>Foster a culture of continuous improvement and mutual support by sharing assessments</p>	<p>List peer review activities in performance reviews.</p> <p>Provide narrative assessments (when reviewing research and researchers) that illustrate how an individual’s peer review activities positively impact their field. Such narratives could complement traditional metrics like scoring, feedback, or certificates by offering a qualitative perspective. Such narrative assessments highlight the broader significance of the reviewer’s contributions, including reflections on the importance of the research reviewed, the influence of their feedback on the publication process, and how their reviews have helped shape the direction of the field.</p>

	<p>standardization of such editorial assessments.</p> <p>Communicate transparently how peer review is incorporated into research assessment.</p>	<p>within a local community of reviewers or a journal's reviewer pool.</p>	
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Conclusions and Limitations

The working group's discussions and the feedback given by experts on our recommendations revealed a nuanced debate about peer review's value in academic and scientific contexts. Our recommendations may not fully capture all the complexities involved. Before delving into specific guidelines for scholarly manuscripts, books, and funding proposals, it is crucial to address several key considerations that emerged from our deliberations.

One of the primary concerns is whether recognition should be based solely on the quantity of peer reviews conducted or if the quality of those reviews should be the primary focus. There was significant debate over the risks of rewarding poorly conducted reviews, and a strong consensus that credit must be linked to the quality and integrity of the review process. In the current system, the quality of peer reviews often remains unknown, particularly in closed review systems where the content and rigor of the reviews are confidential. This lack of transparency raises concerns about the fairness of recognizing peer reviews without a quality assessment. Open peer review systems, which make reviews publicly available, offer a partial solution but have not yet been widely adopted. Moreover, these systems do not address the issue of reviews for manuscripts that are ultimately rejected, leading to lost recognition for the reviewers.

Another central concern is that quantifying or monetizing peer review could lead to superficial or biased assessments. While acknowledging peer review as vital to academic life, the group emphasized it should not be reduced to a mere metric for career advancement. Although some reviewers receive small financial compensations or discounts on article processing charges (APCs), such incentives may encourage hasty, low-quality evaluations, potentially compromising the integrity of the peer review process. While financial incentives might expedite reviews, the consensus was that they are not appropriate and do not help guarantee high-quality, thoughtful feedback. In addition, peer review standards, as well as their integrity, could be improved by providing reviewers with self-assessment tools that allow them to rate their own performance with the help of standardized quality indicators.

The importance of formally acknowledging peer review as a critical component of a researcher's contributions was strongly emphasized. Peer review is often seen as

“care work” and is not typically recognized in formal research (proposal) evaluations or job applications. There was widespread support for including peer review activities in assessment procedures, both at the individual and institutional level. However, establishing metrics that consider both the quantity and quality of peer reviews remains a challenge, as recognition should not come at the cost of academic standards.

In conclusion, while it is crucial to recognize and reward peer review, any system developed for this purpose must carefully balance the quality of reviews, potential conflicts of interest, and the broader implications for academia. Thoughtful consideration is essential when designing recognition and reward systems to ensure they reflect these nuances. While this recommendation paper cannot fully address every concern, it aims to initiate formal recognition and reward for peer review in academia, encouraging further dialogue and refinement of these critical processes.

Chapter 2: Recognizing and Rewarding Peer Review Activities of Scholarly Articles

Introduction

Publication of research outcomes through manuscripts, for example in academic journals, on publication platforms, or on preprint servers, plays a central role in scholarly communication with colleagues, policymakers, and society at large. Although many consider formal peer review of such articles a key element in upholding the quality and integrity of the scientific record and a central part of the scholarly process, the efforts of peer reviewers remain mostly invisible and are typically not formally considered in research assessment – creating a disincentive for researchers to carry out (high-quality) reviews. Developing appropriate recognition and reward systems for quality peer review is important for (i) providing credit to those who contribute to the research community by reviewing the work of colleagues, (ii) aiding in establishing a more diverse and balanced set of performance markers to assess researchers and institutions, and (iii) creating incentives for researchers – including Early Career Researchers (ECRs) – to engage in reviewing activities and to produce high-quality reports.

While the recommendations below refer to the peer review process of scholarly articles published primarily in academic journals, on publication platforms, or as preprints, in accordance with the principles of Open Science, CoARA supports the publication and sharing of various research outputs. These include, but are not limited to, conference outputs, reports, data, metadata, protocols and methods, code and software, images, reporting on null, replicating and refuting results, and other forms of scholarly contributions. While the peer review process and methods of rewarding and incentivizing reviewers may differ, it is crucial to recognize that the basic recommendations apply to all forms of peer-reviewed scholarly output.

Challenges & Limitations

- The recommendations provided in this chapter are particularly relevant to **open or transparent peer review** as these add the most value to the academic community and carry a higher level of accountability, but they can also be applied to other forms of peer review.
- Verification of peer review activities works best when the publication is **Open Access (OA)** (either as preprint or via post-publication OA models).
- There are likely large differences between disciplines in what is considered a high-quality, constructive review report. Careful guidance by editors and

standardization through **structured review reports** (see references below) may help with upholding quality standards, and a **consultative peer review** process (i.e., a process where reviewers can comment on each other's reports, either anonymously or acknowledged) may contribute to upholding the quality of peer review.

- Credit should be given to human-authored review reports, in which AI is used in a limited way to support rather than replace human authorship or accountability.
- The development of suitable **open and community-owned infrastructures** is needed to support an effective reward system for peer review activities because such infrastructures would allow for reviewing activities to be objectively recorded and verified. Such infrastructures should (i) include a mechanism for posting reviews on user profiles and (ii) provide access to review certificates to RPOs and RFOs.
- Any type of reward system for peer reviewing **risks incentivizing undesirable behavior**, such as researchers accepting and completing peer review tasks without ensuring accuracy or quality, especially if the quality is not evaluated by editors. There is also the risk of researchers not disclosing the involvement of other (early career) researchers or the use of AI in their reviews.

Recommendations

Research performing- and research funding organizations

1. Openness

- Encourage researchers to publish in, and review for, journals or platforms that adopt open or transparent peer review models.
- Explore ways to incentivize participation in open peer review that could help foster a more transparent scholarly ecosystem.

2. Credit and Recognition

- Encourage researchers to perform peer review for journals and platforms that provide credit to reviewers (e.g., verifiable certificates or shareable editorial assessments).
- Enable researchers to receive recognition for their review activity by providing CV templates and assessment forms that facilitate and encourage self-reporting of review activity.
- Communicate to the providers of referee reports (referees, journals, funders)

which quality attributes will be included in research assessment of referees.

3. Support, Infrastructure, and Training

- Contribute to the development of digital research infrastructures that make open and transparent review reports openly available and citable (i.e., review hosting platforms).
- Contribute to the development of digital research infrastructures that make verifiable reviewer certificates openly available.
- Provide and incentivize training for researchers to effectively and ethically use these digital research infrastructures.

4. Fairness and Sustainability

- Provide information about the contribution researchers are expected to make to peer review in order to foster a fair and sustainable peer review system.
- Include agreed upon qualitative or quantitative criteria in annual performance assessments, setting defined targets and weighing peer review activity against other performance indicators.

5. Assessment

- Encourage/mandate researchers to list their scholarly article reviews in their CVs, and provide evidence to support this wherever possible (e.g., through certificates or open peer reviews).
- Include review activities in the assessment of researchers in a way that is proportional to that of other scholarly contributions.
- Instruct and train evaluators to include peer review in their assessment.

Editors, publishers, journals, and other platforms

1. Openness

- Adopt open or transparent peer review models, where possible, in favor of double-anonymous peer review (where both authors and reviewers are anonymous to each other).
- Publish reports and author responses side-by-side and in full, from all rounds of revision in a citable manner. Consider generating summaries to make reviewer comments more broadly accessible.

2. Credit and Recognition

- Offer reviewers verifiable certificates of reviewer activity/performance. These could include quality attributes such as (i) frequency of peer review; (ii) thoroughness and constructiveness of reviewer comments; (iii) speed of review;

(iv) assessments or evaluations of reviewer reports by editors, authors, and/or readers, etc.

- Consider incentives for reviewers who deliver high-quality and timely reports, such as meaningful discounts to publication charges.
- Ensure that anyone who assists in the peer review (e.g., trainees or ECRs) is named and included as formal reviewers in credit mechanisms.

3. Support, Infrastructure, and Training

- Contribute to the development of research infrastructures that make signed and unsigned review reports openly available (i.e., review hosting platforms).
- Enable the development of research infrastructures that make verifiable reviewer certificates openly available.
- Provide and incentivize training for researchers to effectively use these digital research infrastructures.

4. Fairness and Sustainability

- Provide information about the potential impact a review report could have on reviewers' future assessment as part of hiring/promotion and funding decisions.

Researchers

1. Openness

- Contribute to journals or platforms that have open (signed or unsigned) peer-review policies.

2. Credit and Recognition

- Perform peer review for journals and platforms that provide credit to reviewers.
- Share review reports openly (signed) or transparently (unsigned) on dedicated review hosting platforms in a citable manner and with a [CC BY license](#), whenever possible.
- Ensure that anyone that assists in the peer review (e.g., trainees or ECRs) is named and included as formal reviewers in credit mechanisms

3. Support, Infrastructure, and Training

- Participate in training in the use of infrastructures for open peer review and for crediting and recognizing reviewers.
- Participate in training on how to deliver fair and constructive peer review.

4. Fairness and Sustainability

- Maintain an appropriate ratio between submitting articles for peer review and performing peer review of articles written by others, in order to equitably distribute

and maintain a balance between submissions and reviews in the academic publishing system.

- Engage in discussions with funding agencies about integrating peer review activity into the evaluation criteria for the funding schemes they review applications for.
- Engage in community discussions on rewarding peer review activity (e.g., CoARA, ASAPbio).

5. Assessment

- Claim reviews as a full-fledged contributions to scholarship by including them in CVs and performance reviews.
- Provide a narrative of how these reviews contribute to the scholarly community.

Selected Resources & Examples of Good Practices

Websites

- ASAPbio. *Publish your reviews*. ASAPbio. <https://asapbio.org/publishyourreviews>
- Review Quality Collector. *Review Quality Collector*. <https://reviewqualitycollector.org/>
- NISO. *Peer review terminology*. National Information Standards Organization. <https://www.niso.org/standards-committees/peer-review-terminology>
- OPUS Project. *Structure peer review to make it more robust*. <https://opusproject.eu>

Articles

- Malički, M., & Mehmani, B. (2024). Structured peer review: Pilot results from 23 Elsevier journals. bioRxiv. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.02.01.578440>
- Ellwanger, J. H., & Chies, J. A. B. (2020). We need to talk about peer-review – Experienced reviewers are not endangered species, but they need motivation. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 125, 201–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2020.02.001>
- Pulverer, B. (2010). A transparent black box. *The EMBO Journal*, 29(23), 3891–3892. <https://doi.org/10.1038/emboj.2010.307>

Chapter 3: Recognizing and Rewarding Peer Review Activities of Scholarly Books

Introduction

Publication of scholarly books plays a central role in the communication of research outcomes, hypotheses, and ideas to colleagues, policymakers, and society at large. In some publication cultures, the formal peer review of scholarly books *before publication* is considered key to upholding the quality and integrity of the scientific record. In other publication cultures, *post-publication review* of scholarly books makes a crucial contribution to the academic discourse through quality filtering and comparative appraisals. Although both pre- and post-publication peer review of books have important roles in scholarly communication, the efforts of peer reviewers remain largely unrecognized and unrewarded during research assessment. Developing appropriate recognition and reward systems for such peer review activities is important to (i) provide credit to those who contribute to the research community by investing time and effort in reviewing the work of colleagues, and (ii) to create incentives for researchers to engage in more reviewing activities and produce higher quality reports.

Challenges & Limitations

- The recommendations provided in this chapter are particularly relevant to **open or transparent peer review** as these add the most value to the academic community and carry a higher level of accountability, but they can also be applied to other forms of peer review.
- Verification of peer review activities works best when the publication is **Open Access (OA)** (either as preprint or via post-publication OA models).
- There are likely large differences between disciplines in what is considered a high-quality, constructive review report. Careful guidance by editors and standardization through **structured review reports** (see references below) may help with upholding quality standards, and a **consultative peer review process** (i.e., a process where reviewers can comment on each other's reports, either anonymously or acknowledged) may contribute to upholding the quality of peer review.
- Credit should be given to human-authored review reports, in which AI is used in a limited way to support rather than replace human authorship or accountability.
- Any type of reward system **risks incentivizing undesirable behavior**, such as researchers accepting and completing peer review tasks without ensuring

accuracy or quality, especially if the quality is not evaluated. There is also the risk of researchers not disclosing the involvement of other (early career) researchers or the use of AI in their reviews.

Recommendations

Research performing- and research funding organizations

1. Openness

- Encourage researchers to publish in, and review for, book publishers that adopt open or transparent peer review models.

2. Credit and Recognition

- Encourage researchers to perform peer review for book publishers that provide credit to reviewers.
- Enable researchers to receive recognition for their review activity by providing CV templates and assessment forms that facilitate and encourage self-reporting of review activity.
- Communicate to the providers of referee reports (referees, journals, funders) which quality attributes will be included in research assessment of referees.

3. Support, Infrastructure, and Training

- Contribute to the development of research infrastructures that make signed and unsigned review reports openly available and citable (i.e., review hosting platforms).
- Enable the development of research infrastructures that make verifiable reviewer certificates openly available.
- Provide and incentivize training for researchers to effectively and ethically use these research infrastructures.

4. Fairness and Sustainability

- Provide information about the contribution researchers are expected to make to peer review in order to foster a fair and sustainable peer review system.
- Include agreed upon qualitative or quantitative criteria in annual performance assessments, setting defined targets and weighing peer review activity against other performance indicators.

5. Assessment

- Encourage/mandate researchers to list their book reviews in their CVs and provide evidence to support this wherever possible (e.g., through certificates or open peer

reviews).

- Include book reviews in assessments of researchers in a way that is proportional to other scholarly contributions.
- Instruct and train evaluators to include peer review in their assessment.

Editors, publishers, journals, and other platforms

1. Openness

- Adopt open or transparent peer review models in lieu of double-anonymous peer review (where both authors and reviewers are anonymous to each other).
- Publish reports and author responses side-by-side and in full, from all rounds of revision in a citable manner. Consider generating summaries to make reviewer comments more broadly accessible.

2. Credit and Recognition

- Offer reviewers verifiable certificates of reviewer activity/performance. These could include quality attributes such as (i) frequency of peer review; (ii) thoroughness and helpfulness of reviewer comments; (iii) timeliness of reviewer; (iv) assessments or evaluations of reviewer reports by editors, authors, and/or readers, etc.
- Consider incentives for reviewers who deliver high-quality and timely reports, such as meaningful discounts to publication charges.
- Ensure that anyone who assists in the peer review (e.g., trainees or ECRs) is named and included as formal reviewers in credit mechanisms.

3. Support, Infrastructure, and Training

- Contribute to the development of research infrastructures that make signed and unsigned review reports openly available (i.e., review hosting platforms).
- Enable the development of research infrastructures that make verifiable reviewer certificates openly available.
- Provide and incentivize training for researchers to effectively use these infrastructures.
- Consider creating journals dedicated to reviews in a given subject area: an example of such a review-oriented journal is [Lectures](#).

4. Fairness and Sustainability

- Provide information about the potential impact a review report could have on reviewers' future assessment as part of hiring/promotion and funding decisions.

Researchers

1. Openness

- Contribute to book publishers that have open (signed or unsigned) peer-review policies.

2. Credit and Recognition

- Perform peer review for book publishers that provide credit to reviewers.
- Share review reports openly (signed) or transparently (unsigned) on dedicated review hosting platforms in a citable manner and with a [CC BY license](#), whenever possible.
- Ensure that anyone who assists in peer review (e.g., trainees or ECRs) is named and included as formal reviewers in credit mechanisms

3. Support, Infrastructure, and Training

- Participate in training in the use of infrastructures for open peer review and for crediting and recognizing reviewers.

4. Fairness and Sustainability

- Consider doing book reviews as a constructive contribution to the scholarly conversation.
- Engage in discussions with funding agencies about integrating peer review activity into the evaluation criteria for the funding schemes they review applications for.
- Engage in community discussions on rewarding peer review activity (e.g., CoARA, ASAPbio).

5. Assessment

- Claim reviews as a full-fledged contributions to scholarship by including them in CVs and performance reviews.
- Provide a narrative of how these reviews contribute to the scholarly community.

Selected Resources & Examples of Good Practices

Websites & Reports

- PRISM. PRISM: Peer Review Information Service for Monographs. Directory of Open Access Books. <https://www.doabooks.org/en/article/prism>
- PreReview. PreReview platform. <https://prereview.org/>
- Open Science Career Assessment Matrix: European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Cabello Valdes, C., Rentier, B., Kaunismaa, E.,

Metcalf, J., Esposito, F., McAllister, D., Maas, K., Vandeveld, K., & O'Carroll, C. (Eds.). (2017). *Evaluation of research careers fully acknowledging Open Science practices: Rewards, incentives and/or recognition for researchers practicing Open Science*. Publications Office of the European Union.

<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/75255>

- Norwegian Career Assessment Matrix: Universities Norway (UHR). (2021). *NOR-CAM: A toolbox for recognition and rewards in academic careers*. Universities Norway. https://www.uhr.no/en/_f/p3/i86e9ec84-3b3d-48ce-8167-bbae0f507ce8/nor-cam-a-tool-box-for-assessment-and-rewards.pdf; An example of this in practice: University of Stavanger. (2023). *UiS-CAM career assessment matrix for teaching and research posts*. University of Stavanger. <https://www.uis.no/sites/default/files/2023-06/UiS-CAM%20Career%20Assessment%20Matrix%20for%20teaching%20and%20research%20posts.pdf> uhr.no+5uis.no+5uis.no+5

Structure of Peer Review for Scholarly Books

The structure of peer reviews for scholarly books is discussed here:

- Wiley. Reviewing published books. <https://authorservices.wiley.com/Reviewers/book-reviewers/reviewing-published-books.html>
- Sato, K. (2020). Book review: Getting published in academic journals: Navigating the publication process. *RELC Journal*, 51(1), 174-177. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0033688220916239>
- Cambridge University Press. A guide to peer reviewing book proposals. <https://www.cambridge.org/core/services/aop-file-manager/file/5a1eb62839b03b2b0605becf/Refreshed-Guide-Peer-Review-Books.pdf>

A typical structure for a peer review of a scholarly book looks as follows:

1. **Introduction:** Contextualization. Why is this book of interest, unique, or timely? Who is the author and why are they competent? What is its target audience?
2. **Summary:** Methods, results, major contribution.
3. **Critical analysis:** How does the book contribute to the research area and what are its limits? Point out strengths & weaknesses; the originality of ideas; flaws in reasoning/argumentation; inadequate evidence; gaps and superfluous material. Compare the book to similar books/research. Is the language clear and accessible?
4. **Conclusion:** Major contributions, takeaways, and criticisms.

General recommendations while writing a book review include the following:

1. Be as critical as needed but fair to the author. Try to balance positive and negative points.
2. Back up your arguments with evidence and examples, provide quotations from the book as necessary.
3. Be brief (e.g., 3000–5000 words, depending on the publisher/editor).

Other Useful Links

- O’Neill, J. (2023). The necessity of book reviews. The Scholarly Kitchen. <https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2023/11/17/the-necessity-of-book-reviews/>
- Tomaselli, K. G. (2022). Book reviewing should be a measurable academic output. *University World News*. <https://www.universityworldnews.com/post.php?story=20220418043931171>
- Lee, A. D., Green, B. N., Johnson, C. D., & Nyquist, J. (2010). How to write a scholarly book review for publication in a peer-reviewed journal: a review of the literature. *The Journal of chiropractic education*, 24(1), 57–69. <https://doi.org/10.7899/1042-5055-24.1.57>
- Guerin, C., Aitchison, C., & Carter, S. (2024). *Creating, managing, and editing multi-authored publications: A guide for scholars* (1st ed., Insider Guides to Success in Academia). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003287117>
- Committee on Publication Ethics. Guidance – COPE. <https://publicationethics.org/guidance?f%5B0%5D=topics%3A22>
- Review Quality Collector. *Review Quality Collector*. <https://reviewqualitycollector.org/>
- Liu, W., Ding, Y., & Gu, M. (2017). Book reviews in academic journals: Patterns and dynamics. *Scientometrics*, 110(1), 355–364. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-2172-2>

Chapter 4: Recognizing and Rewarding Peer Review Activities of Funding Proposals

Introduction

The current research ecosystem relies significantly on external support from private and public funding agencies to finance research activities. Researchers apply for such funding by submitting research proposals which, due to the increasing competition for limited funding available, undergo quality control and selection by peers to identify the most promising proposals. Peer review of funding proposals is considered key to uphold the quality of the research funded and arrive at fair and justifiable decisions that may have a fundamental impact on the applicants' career and the creation of knowledge. However the efforts of peer reviewers in funding proposal assessment remain largely unnoticed. Peer reviewing is often simply considered a routine aspect of an academic's job, and researchers invest a substantial portion of their time in it without receiving any recognition for it, as it is not broadly acknowledged for career advancement or employment. Developing appropriate recognition and reward mechanisms for peer reviewing funding proposals is essential for (i) acknowledging the contributions of reviewers who invest time and effort in evaluating colleagues' proposals, (ii) incentivizing researchers to engage in high-quality research proposal reviewing activities, and (iii) maintaining a research project selection system of robust quality.

Our emphasis on academic recognition does not exclude financial incentives; rather, it reflects a broader commitment to reforming research assessment practices. Here, we do not aim to compare or rank different kinds of recognition, we simply focus on a mode of recognition that has hitherto received less attention but enables and supports important values necessary for scientific endeavor.

Challenges & Limitations

- In the context of funding allocation, “peer review” can encompass a variety of activities used to assess applications and submit evaluations to funding agencies (see Annex). Funding agencies often require a combination of them, and this varies across funding schemes. These differences may stem from state regulations, disciplinary differences or the individual missions of funding organizations. This variation makes it particularly challenging to develop a universal definition of the quality of peer review activity for funding allocation.
- Verification of peer review for funding allocation is extremely challenging due to the **confidentiality** of both proposals and reviewers' reports. Funders face

significant hurdles in adopting transparency as they must protect researchers' ideas, especially in military, dual-use, commercial, or legally sensitive cases such as those involving data privacy. While confidentiality helps prevent bias, misconduct, and legal violations, it also limits transparency by delaying the release of proposals and reports until after research is completed.

- In some cases, reviewers only score and rank proposals without written reports, making feedback even harder to share. Although review panel members' names are sometimes disclosed, individual reviewers remain anonymous, complicating efforts to verify peer review at the researcher level. **Balancing transparency and confidentiality** remains a key challenge in ensuring both fairness and accountability.
- Given the complexity of the peer review process for funding allocation, it might be **impossible to evaluate the quality** of a researcher's review activity, although standardized **structured review reports** may contribute to this. Publicly listing the names of reviewers (without attribution to specific proposals) or providing a certificate that validates engagement in the process, without stating its quality, might be sufficient to recognize, reward, and incentivize this activity. However, it is crucial to consider whether merely stating involvement in peer review for a specific agency is sufficient, or if the quality of their review work should also be communicated.
- Any type of reward system **risks incentivizing undesirable behavior**, such as researchers accepting and completing peer review tasks without ensuring accuracy or quality, especially if the quality is not evaluated. There is also the risk of researchers not disclosing the involvement of other (early career) researchers or the use of AI in their reviews.

Recommendations

Research performing- and research funding organizations (as evaluators)

1. Openness

- Encourage peer review contributions to funders who can demonstrate that the quality of the reviewers and review process are vetted, for example by (i) establishing clearer and more coherent conflict-of-interest guidelines, and (ii) considering the development of a system of quality indicators for reviewers to improve transparency at an early stage (i.e., without linking their activity to individual proposals).

2. Credit and Recognition

- Encourage researchers to perform peer review for funding agencies that provide recognition (such as publicly listing the names of reviewers, or providing certificates that validate their contributions) to reviewers.
- Enable researchers to receive recognition for their review activity by providing CV templates and assessment forms that facilitate and encourage reporting of review activity.

3. Support, Infrastructure, and Training

- Contribute to the development of research infrastructures that make verifiable reviewer certificates (openly) available.
- Provide and incentivize training for researchers to effectively use these infrastructures.
- Provide and incentivize training for evaluators in expert panels in order to improve the quality and objectivity of their work.

4. Fairness and Sustainability

- RPOs need to provide information about the contribution researchers are expected to make to peer review in order to foster a fair and sustainable peer review system.
- Include agreed upon qualitative or quantitative criteria in annual performance assessments, setting defined targets and weighing peer review activity against other quality indicators.

5. Assessment

- Ask researchers to list (a selection of) their funding proposal reviews in their CVs and provide evidence to support this wherever possible (e.g., through certificates, public lists, or open peer reviews).
- Include funding proposal reviews in assessments of researchers in a way that is proportional to other scholarly contributions.
- Instruct and train evaluators to include peer review in their assessment.

Funding organizations (as coordinators of peer review)

1. Openness

- Demonstrate that the quality of the reviewers and review process are vetted, for example by (i) establishing clearer and more coherent conflict-of-interest guidelines and (ii) implementing a system of quality indicators for reviewers to improve transparency (i.e., without linking their activity to individual proposals).

2. Credit and Recognition

- Offer reviewers verifiable certificates of reviewer activity/performance. These could include quality attributes such as (i) frequency of peer review; (ii) thoroughness of reviewer comments; (iii) timeliness of reviewer; (iv) internal scoring of reviewer reports, etc.
- Experiment with incentive mechanisms beyond financial compensation. For example, applicants could review the proposals of their competitors. This method was used by the US National Science Foundation Division of Civil, Mechanical and Manufacturing Innovation (CMMI) (see [report by EMBO](#)) and is currently being tested by the Volkswagen Foundation in the call [Open up](#)). Additional experiments with incentives for peer reviewers, such as social benefits or extension of the duration of projects, are ongoing and should be explored further.

3. Support, Infrastructure, and Training

- Contribute to the development of research infrastructures that make verifiable reviewer certificates openly available.
- Provide and incentivize training for researchers to effectively and ethically use these infrastructures.

4. Fairness and Sustainability

- Provide information about the potential impact a review report could have on reviewers' future assessment as part of hiring and funding decisions.

Researchers

1. Openness

- Engage in discussions with RFOs and RPOs about integrating peer review activity into the evaluation criteria for funding schemes they review applications for, and for hiring and promotions, respectively.

2. Credit and Recognition

- Perform peer review for RFOs that share information on their reviewers (without attribution to specific proposals) and/or provide a certificate verifying the reviewer's activity and describing their role within the evaluation process.

3. Support, Infrastructure, and Training

- Participate in training to effectively use new peer review/assessment infrastructures.
- Participate in training for evaluators in expert panels in order to improve the quality and objectivity of such work.

4. Fairness and Sustainability

- Maintain an appropriate ratio between submitting funding proposals for peer review and reviewing funding proposals written by others, in order to renormalize the balance between submissions and reviews within the peer review system.
- Engage in discussions with funding agencies about integrating peer review activity into the evaluation criteria for funding schemes they review applications for.
- Engage in community discussions on rewarding peer review activity (e.g., CoARA).

5. Assessment

- Claim reviews as a full-fledged contributions to scholarship by including them in CVs and performance reviews.
- Provide a narrative of how these reviews contribute to the scholarly community.

Selected Resources & Examples of Good Practices

- Hug, S.E., Aeschbach, M. (2020). Criteria for assessing grant applications: a systematic review. *Palgrave Communications* 6(37).
<https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-020-0412-9>
- Superchi, C., González, J. A., Solà, I., Dwan, K., Hren, D., & Moja, L. (2019). Tools used to assess the quality of peer review reports: A methodological systematic review. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 19(48). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-019-0688-x>
- EMBO. (2021). *Dealing with the limits of peer review with innovative approaches to allocating research funding* [Report].
https://www.embo.org/documents/science_policy/peer_review_report.pdf
- Research on Research Institute. (2024). Volkswagen Foundation introduces experimental Distributed Peer Review.
<https://researchonresearch.org/volkswagen-distributed-peer-review/>

Annex: Different Peer Review Roles in Research Funding Organizations

An overview of the reviewer types within a funding organization is provided in **Table 2** to illustrate the diverse reviewers and reviewing activities that may occur within such organizations. This distinction is crucial because reviewing processes within funding agencies significantly differ from those of journal reviewers. Funding organizations employ diverse methods for organizing peer review, which can vary based on the specific funding schemes they oversee. The goal of this overview is to provide insight into this complexity, fostering transparency within the research ecosystem. It is important to note that while the table presented in this document offers valuable information, it does not exhaustively cover the various aspects of peer review within funding agencies.

Table 2: Overview of Reviewer Types in Funding Agencies

Reviewer Type	Definition	Selection
Internal	Reviewer employed within the funding agency, responsible for assessing proposals	Appointed by the agency
External	Academic or industry expert invited from outside the agency to evaluate proposals; Specialized reviewer chosen for their expertise in a particular field or subject area relevant to the proposals	Appointed by the agency - Selected based on specific knowledge areas and experience
Audit	Reviewer tasked with verifying compliance and adherence to regulations within the funding process	Typically appointed by regulatory bodies or funding agencies
Panelist	Reviewer participating in a panel review process, contributing to collective decision-making on funding allocations	Appointed by the agency - Selected for panel diversity and expertise

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These recommendations have been developed by the [CoARA Working Group on Recognizing and Rewarding Peer Review](#) (see members listed below in alphabetical order). Working groups are central to CoARA's mission to enable systemic reform of research assessment. Based on a bottom-up approach with members' voluntary involvement, working groups operate as 'communities of practice', providing mutual learning and collaboration on specific thematic areas. Participating members exchange knowledge, learn from each other's experience, discuss and develop outputs to advance research assessment, and support the implementation of members' commitments.

About the Drafting & Consultation Process

This set of recommendations was drafted by the CoARA Working Group on Recognizing and Rewarding Peer Review, led by the three Co-Chairs, **Tung Tung Chan** (Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam), **Bernd Pulverer** (EMBO Press), and **Johan Rooryck** (cOAlition S). The Working Group circulated drafts of the recommendations (August 2024–April 2025) to the wider CoARA community and collected feedback. While the Working Group considered all the constructive insights from the CoARA community in detail, it exercised its editorial judgment in responding to, and incorporating, the feedback to develop the final set of recommendations presented here. The Co-Chairs and members of the Working Group bear ultimate responsibility for this document.

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